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AN ANALYTIC MODEL OF PSYCHO-SOCIAL VARIABLES AS DETERMINANTS OF CHEATING TENDENCY AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study is a path modelling, which examined the effect and magnitude of six psycho-social variables on students' tendency to cheat in examinations. Questionnaire data were generated from 600 secondary school students in 10 schools in Cross River State. Results of data analysis using path analysis procedure indicated that only five psycho-social factors were effective in explaining the students' tendency to cheat in an examination. Test anxiety and attribution for hard -work had the most significant influence on students' tendency to cheat. In all, 77.43% of the total effect of the variables was direct, while 22.5% was indirect. The implications of the research findings were addressed.

Keywords: Path Modelling, Psycho-Social, Cheating tendency, Examination

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, education in Nigeria is bleeding profusely from the wounds inflicted on it by cheating in examinations. From the basic level education through the secondary to tertiary levels, cheating in examinations has attained a gargantuan proportion that is beyond the comprehension of ordinary mind (Iredia, 2002). Consequently, students are awarded grades that do not reflect the true picture of the quantity of attributes they possess. In other words, students carry certificates that they cheated their way to obtain and hence, cannot defend.

Perhaps the so call "fallen standard" may have its root from this ill wind, called cheating in examinations. Unfortunately, all efforts made by school managements and even the governments appear to be creating no impact, in terms of eliminating this tendency to cheat in examinations among our students. Awonusi (2002) opined that the main motivator of the tendency to cheat among students is the "get-rich-quick" philosophy of the society which he argued, had translated to "get-certificate-quick" syndrome, an act which invalidates and makes nonsense of the educational certificates awarded by the system.

Available literature reveals the existence of relationships between some psycho-social factors and the tendency to cheat. Commenting on the tendency to cheat among students, Udom (1986) asserted that students with parents from different socioeconomic status differ significantly in their self-reported tendency to cheat. Isangedighi (1997) also provided evidence to show that the effective study habit can result in maximal achievement of students in tests and examinations. Other variables identified by researchers as relating to the tendency to cheat included: - achievement motivation (Nyenti, 1991 & Alarape and Onakoya, 2003); self-concept (Ukpong 2000 & Enu (2001); test-anxiety (Udom, 1986); and attribution for hard work (Paulman & Kennelly, 1984, Alarape and Onakoya, 2003).

Lacking in these studies, however, is data on direct and indirect effect of these variables, or factors on students' tendency to cheat. It is hoped that a better understanding of the interactions between some psycho-social factors and the tendency to cheat, when considered simultaneously would provide scope and direction, hence, this present study. The general

purpose of this study is to evaluate the interrelationship among measures of psycho-social factors and students' tendency to cheat in examinations. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following research questions:

- What are the significant paths in the six-variable model through which the independent-variables determine students' tendency to cheat in an examination?
- What is the most meaningful causal model involving the six psycho-social variables, and students' tendency to cheat in an examination?
- What are the direct and indirect effects of the psycho-social variables, on students' tendency to cheat in an examination?
- What proportions (%) of the total effects are direct and indirect?

2. METHOD AND MATERIALS

The respondents for the study involved 600 students from 10 secondary schools in 5 Local Government Areas of Southern Education Zone (SEZ) of Cross River State; (300 males and 300 females) selected through stratified random sampling technique. The age ranges from 15 to 19 with a mean age of 16.6. A questionnaire was used for data collection. The questionnaire had 4 sections. Section A sought to elicit demographic information. Section B of the questionnaire dealt with parental socioeconomic status with 10 items. The third and fourth sections dealt with 5 independent variables (30 items) and the students' tendency to cheat (10 items) respectively. A split half reliability estimates ranging from 0.76 to 0.95 were obtained for all the sub-scales. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents with the help of research assistants.

Path analysis was adopted to explain the students' tendency to cheat from psycho-social factors. This statistical technique (with the aid of SPSS) was computed to provide answers to the research questions; the linear relationship between the six psycho-social variables and the dependent variable (students' tendency to cheat) forms the basis for hypothesizing a theoretical model shown in figure 1, with seven variables under consideration. Structural modeling as defined by Blalock (1964) is a technique for selecting those variables that are perceived to be determinants (causes) of the effects and then attempting to isolate the separate contributions to the effects made by each cause through the application of path analysis technique. The variables in figure 1 are represented as follows:

- X_1 = Socio-economic status
- X_2 = Study habit
- X_3 = Achievement motivation
- X_4 = Self-concept
- X_5 = Test anxiety
- X_6 = Attribution to hardwork
- X_7 = cheating tendency

Figure 1: Hypothesized structural model

In the model, $e_1, e_2 \dots e_7$ are residual variables (to indicate the effects of variables outside the model that were not accounted for by the independent variables). $P_{21}, P_{31}, P_{41} \dots P_{76}$ are paths drawn from variables taken as causes (independent variables) to variables taken as effects (dependent).

The basic aim of the path analysis is to enable one to understand patterns of relationship between the six psycho-social variables and the dependent variable. The principle underlying the use of path analysis in this study is based on assumptions by Kerlinger (1986) as follows:

- The relations among the variables in the model are linear, additive and causal;
- There is a one-way causal flow in the system, i.e. No reciprocal causation;
- The residuals are not correlated among themselves and with the variables preceding them in the model;
- Each of endogenous (dependent) variable is directly related to all the variables preceding it in the hypothesized causal sequence.

The hypothesized path model which addressed the linkages between the sets of variables in this study is presented as figure 1. According to Turner and Stevens (1959), in a study involving only 3 variables, with at least one being exogenous, there are six possible path models, while for a 4-variable study, 65 diagrams are possible, and so on. Hence, the hypothesized model in figure 1 is not the only version possible. Therefore, the use of confirmatory model requires the selection of the most meaningful path diagrams for all possible ones. The process of identifying and trimming the paths in the model was undertaken. The investigators identified the important paths in the model by constructing the relevant structural equations using the technique of path analysis theorem and Wrights law. For the trimming of the paths in the model, the criteria of statistical significance and meaningfulness were used. These 2 criteria were applied to properly trim the model in order to provide a more adequate testing of the theory under consideration. To be meaningful, the absolute value of the path coefficients should be at least .05 as recommended by Land (1969). The structural equation for the hypothesized model is presented as follows and also shown in figure 1:

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= e_1 \\ X_2 &= P_{21}X_1 + e_2 \\ X_3 &= P_{32}X_2 + P_{31}X_1 + e_3 \end{aligned}$$

$$X_4 = P_{43}X_3 + P_{42}X_2 + P_{41}X_1 + e_4$$

$$X_5 = P_{54}X_4 + P_{53}X_3 + P_{52}X_2 + P_{51}X_1 + e_5$$

$$X_6 = P_{65}X_5 + P_{64}X_4 + P_{63}X_3 + P_{62}X_2 + P_{61}X_1 + e_6$$

$$X_7 = P_{76}X_6 + P_{75}X_5 + P_{74}X_4 + P_{73}X_3 + P_{72}X_2 + P_{71}X_1 + e_7$$

3. RESULTS

(a) Causal effect of psycho-social variables on students' tendency to cheat in examinations

To determine the path coefficients in the hypothesized path model, path analysis technique was utilized. Table 1 shows the various path coefficients (expressed in beta weights) in the path model and their level of significance. Paths whose coefficients are significant at .01 probability level was retained (Table 1) otherwise, they were not strong and therefore, trimmed. This made it possible to have a more parsimonious model.

Table 1: Significant paths through which the psycho-social variables determine students' cheating tendency in examination

Paths	Path coefficient	P-level
P ₂₁	0.287	.000**
P ₃₁	0.232	.000**
P ₃₂	0.487	.000**
P ₄₁	0.139	.000**
P ₄₂	0.245	.000**
P ₄₃	0.322	.000**
P ₅₁	-0.191	.000**
P ₅₂	-0.084	.034*
P ₅₃	-0.149	.000**
P ₅₄	-0.384	.000**
P ₆₁	0.144	.000**
P ₆₂	0.063	.096 _{NS}
P ₆₃	0.245	.000**
P ₆₄	0.31	.000**
P ₆₅	-0.109	.006 _{NS}
P ₇₁	-0.126	.000**
P ₇₂	-0.066	.059 _{NS}
P ₇₃	-0.144	.000**
P ₇₄	-0.205	.000**
P ₇₅	0.243	.000**
P ₇₆	-0.219	.000**

NS = not significant at .05 level

* = Significant at .05 level

** = significant at .01 level

Table 1 shows the paths in the hypothesized recursive model, the standardized path coefficients and the level of significance for each of the path coefficients. The result shows that the standardized path coefficients ranged from .063 for P₆₂ to .487 for P₃₂. The result also shows that out of the 21 paths in the hypothesized model, 17 were significant at .01 levels; one path (P₅₂) was significant at .05 level while 3 paths (P₆₂, P₆₅ & P₇₂) were not significant at .01 level. On the basis of these results, 17 paths significant at .01 level were retained while the other one path (P₅₂) significant at .05 level and these paths (P₆₂, P₆₅, P₇₂) not significant at .05 level, were trimmed. In all, four paths were trimmed out since they were considered weak paths, not strong enough to be included in the new model.

(b) Structural Equations for the New Parsimonious Model

$$\begin{aligned}
 X_1 &= e_1 \\
 X_2 &= P_{21}X_1 + e_2 \\
 X_3 &= P_{32}X_2 + P_{31}X_1 + e_3 \\
 X_4 &= P_{43}X_3 + P_{42}X_2 + P_{41}X_1 + e_4 \\
 X_5 &= P_{54}X_4 + P_{53}X_3 + P_{51}X_1 + e_5 \\
 X_6 &= P_{64}X_4 + P_{63}X_3 + P_{62}X_2 + P_{61}X_1 + e_6 \\
 X_7 &= P_{76}X_6 + P_{75}X_5 + P_{74}X_4 + P_{73}X_3 + P_{71} + e_7
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the above equations, the new hypothesized model was obtained as shown in figure 2. Figure 2 shows that only 17 out of the 21 hypothesized paths survived the trimming exercise. The numbers on each pathway are coefficients and the zero order correlation coefficients are in parentheses.

Figure 2: The new parsimonious model (the trimmed model)

(c) Validation Of The New Model

To verify the efficacy of the new model, the reproduced correlation coefficients (using the new path model) were compared to the original correlation coefficients. Table 2 shows original and reproduced coefficient matrix.

Table 2: Coefficient Matrix

Variables	SES(X ₁)	STH(X ₂)	ACM(X ₃)	SCC(X ₄)	TAX(X ₅)	ATT(X ₆)	TTC(X ₇)
SES(X ₁)	1.000	.287	.372	.328	-.397	.398	-.449
STH(X ₂)	.287(P ₂₁)	1.000	.554	.463	-.399	.427	-.465
ACM(X ₃)	.232(P ₃₁)	.487(P ₃₂)	1.000	.509	-.462	.542	-.562
SCC(X ₄)	.139(P ₄₁)	.245(P ₄₂)	.322(P ₄₃)	1.000	-.562	.572	-.611
TAX(X ₅)	-	-	-.149(P ₅₃)	-	1.000	-.479	.605
ATT(X ₆)	.191(P ₆₁)	.084(P ₆₂)	.245(P ₆₃)	.384(P ₆₄)	-	1.000	-.608
TTC(X ₇)	-	-	-.144(P ₇₃)	-	.109(P ₇₅)	-	1.000
	.126(P ₇₁)	.066(P ₇₂)	-	.205(P ₇₄)	.243(P ₇₅)	.219(P ₇₆)	-

- X_1 = Socio-economic status (SES)
 X_2 = Study habit (STH)
 X_3 = Achievement motivation (ACM)
 X_4 = Self-concept (SCC)
 X_5 = Test anxiety (TAX)
 X_6 = Attribution to hardwork (ATT)
 X_7 = cheating tendency (TTC)

(d) *Proportions of total Direct and Indirect Effects*

The path analysis technique was also utilized to provide data on the total effect, total direct effect, and total indirect effect. Based on these, the percentages of direct and indirect effects relative to the total effects were determined. The summary of results of this analysis is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Proportion of totals and indirect effects

Variables	Total effect	Direct effects	% of direct effect	Indirect effect	% of indirect effect
Socio-economic status (X_1)	-.449	-.126	6.03	-.323	15.5
Study habit (X_2)	-.465	-	-	-.465	22.25
Achievement motivation (X_3)	-.562	-.144	6.89	-.418	20.0
Self-concept (X_4)	-.611	-.205	9.80	-.406	19.4
Test anxiety (X_5)	.605	.243	-11.63	.362	-17.3
Attribution to hardwork (X_6)	-.608	-.219	10.48	-.389	18.6
Total	-2.090	-.45	21.57	-1.639	78.43

Table 3 shows the total effects (direct and indirect) of all the six-predictor variables as well as the percentages of direct and indirect effects. The results in the table show that out of the six psycho-social variables, five (SES, ACM, SCC, TAX and ATT) exert both direct and indirect effects on the dependent variable. However, one variable, (STH) exerts only indirect effect (-.465) on the dependent variable. No direct effect was observed with respect to this variable. The table also shows the proportion of the total effects that are direct (21.57%) and indirect (78.43%) respectively. These percentages indicate that the six psycho-social variables used in this study exert more of an indirect than direct effect on students' cheating tendency.

4. DISCUSSIONS

The result of path analysis in Table 1 revealed that six psycho-social variables (i.e. Socioeconomic status, study habit, achievement motivation, self-concept, test anxiety and attribution for hard work) taken together, are effective in predicting cheating tendency among students sampled for this study. Since the magnitude of beta weights is taken to be directly proportional to the degree of effects of the independent variable, it can be seen from Table 3, that 5 variables (variables 1,3,4,5 & 6) have a direct causal effect on students' cheating tendency. Test anxiety (variable 5) has the most effective causal effect on students' cheating tendency. As shown in table 3, variable five (5) has a path coefficient of .243 significant at .01 level. This empirical finding is not unexpected considering the previous researchers (Nenty, 1995; Isangedighi, 1997) have shown that test anxiety has a significant effect on students' examination and test-taking behavior. More so, a high level of test anxiety is likely to result in poor performance, and such students would want to cheat in order to pass. Attribution for hard

work is the next variable that has a direct causal effect on students' cheating tendency in the examination. It has a path co-efficient of -.219, at .01 level of significance. This finding does not agree with the finding of Nenty (1989) on the attribution patterns of students. Of course, as an internal form of attribution, i.e. attribution to a more stable factor, it is expected to impact less on the tendency to cheat. The corollary of this is that those who attribute their performance externally to luck and task difficulty, exhibited a higher level of anxiety, which correlates highly with the tendency to cheat than internals who attribute to effort and ability.

Other direct causes are academic self-concept, achievement motivation and socioeconomic status. Their findings corroborated some previous findings (Nyenti, 1991; Enu, 2001; Agbor, 2004). However, the effect of study habit seems to be only indirect. This result perhaps, suggests that in the presence of other more potent variables, the direct effect of study habit would be low and not statistically significant and meaningful.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of these findings, it could be concluded that cheating tendency can be explained with variables that surround the students. The relative importance of these psychosocial variables, are shown in the following relationship: $X_5 > X_6 > X_4 > X_3 > X_1 > X_2$. In other words, test anxiety (X_5) and attribution for hard work (X_6) had the most significant influence on students' tendency to cheat while the last was studying habit. Further studies should focus on home factors and determinants of students' tendency to cheat in an examination.

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